

ORCAS Community Workshop

Workshop title:	<i>The ORCAS Community Workshop: Connecting Observations and AI Sea Ice Prediction Systems</i>
Organisers:	ORCAS (Observational Requirements in the Context of AI prediction systems for Sea ice), a SCOR Working Group and PCAPS Task Team.
Dates:	February 10 & 11, 2026 (Two sessions held to accommodate global time zones).

Link to session 1 recording:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1g4C8V6HIQLFHZ4CIFSvUPZW69oPXXwPV/view?usp=drive_link

Link to session 2 recording:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jDI8W5TI4VoOemIFuKltZCn8Dn68UyUF/view?usp=drive_link

Workshop attendees: Clare Eayrs (NYU), Lorenzo Zampieri (ECMWF), Simon Driscoll (University of Cambridge, Department of Applied Mathematics and Theoretical Physics), Yafei Nie (Sun Yat-sen University), Julien Brajard (NERSC), Mitch Bushuk (NOAA GFDL), Will Gregory (Princeton University), Isabel Fenton (The Alan Turing Institute), Luisa von Albedyll (AWI), Tian Tian (DMI), Wayne De Jager (University of Cape Town), Zachary Labe (Climate Central Inc.), François Massonnet (UCLouvain), Andrew McDonald (University of Cambridge & British Antarctic Survey), Martin Rogers (British Antarctic Survey), Lauren Hoffman (University of California), Xinlong Liu (University of Tasmania)

1. Executive Summary

The ORCAS Community Workshop brought together 15 participants from operational centres, academic institutions, and non-profit organisations across five continents to build a community around the intersection of AI sea ice prediction and observational science. Nine attendees identified as early career, highlighting that the shift toward AI in polar prediction is being strongly driven by the next generation of researchers. The expertise spanned AI and physical modellers, observationalists, and researchers working at the interface between the two.

Four presentations set the scene, covering ORCAS' mission and institutional context, the "noisy revolution" in AI sea ice forecasting, the use of AI in field campaigns such as MOSAiC, and the diverse needs of end users from maritime operators to climate services. Sub-seasonal to seasonal (S2S) sea ice prediction was identified as the primary initial focus, though the community recognised the importance of shorter and longer timescales and the need to determine how far ORCAS should extend beyond S2S.

The facilitated discussions identified a clear niche for ORCAS: *evaluating the physical realism of AI predictions through stress-testing and perturbation experiments, complementing rather than duplicating the forecast skill intercomparisons already conducted by initiatives such as SIPN South*. To support this, the community called for curating campaign and process-study datasets into targeted validation suites organised around key physical themes, guided by a principle of "collection, not perfection." Participants also discussed Direct Observation Prediction as a promising complement to reanalysis-based training, and graph neural network approaches for ingesting sparse, heterogeneous polar observations. On model diversity, the consensus favoured a diverse ecosystem of tailored systems over a single dominant architecture, with ORCAS providing common data and evaluation frameworks usable across different model types and scales. Key data gaps identified included Antarctic sea ice thickness and snow depth, the lack of long continuous records beyond concentration, the lag in real-time data availability for operational AI systems, and cross-scale linkages between point observations and basin-scale products.

A recurring theme was the need for early co-design between field scientists and AI modellers, with ORCAS facilitating feedback loops so that future campaign design, sampling strategies, and data processing are shaped by what AI systems can actually use.

2. Workshop Attendees

15 attendees joined over the two sessions. The 15 attendees represented roughly half of the 31 registrations received, with the remainder unable to attend due to scheduling constraints but requesting to be kept informed of ORCAS activities. The workshop participants were largely observationalists (field and remote sensing) and modellers (AI and physical). Nine attendees identified as Early Career, highlighting that the shift towards AI in polar prediction is being strongly driven by the next generation of researchers. The geographic spread included:

- **Europe:** ECMWF (Germany), AWI (Germany), NERSC (Norway), DMI (Denmark), Alan Turing Institute/BAS (UK), UCLouvain (Belgium)
- **North America:** NOAA GFDL, Princeton, NYU, UC Santa Cruz, Climate Central (USA)

- **Asia:** Sun Yat-sen University (China)
- **Africa:** University of Cape Town (South Africa)
- **Oceania:** University of Tasmania (Australia)

Registrations were received from all six inhabited continents, including South America, indicating broad global interest in the intersection of AI prediction and sea ice observations. Growing this community remains a priority for ORCAS, and the mailing list and future workshops will serve as key mechanisms for bringing the wider registered community into ongoing activities.

Participant expertise was roughly split into three clusters:

- **AI and modellers:** developers of specific architectures (e.g. IceNet, ConvLSTM, IceCastNet) and those integrating AI into operational frameworks (e.g. ECMWF AIFS, DMI IcyAlert)
- **Observationalists:** experts in sensor data, including Antarctic altimetry (freeboard/thickness), ship-based radar (deformation), and field campaigns (MOSAIC)
- **Hybrid/integrators:** researchers working at the interface, such as parameter tuning via machine learning, melt pond emulation, and explaining AI (XAI) for physical consistency.

The table summarises what the community needs from ORCAS and what it can offer in return.

What the Community needs from ORCAS	What the Community can offer ORCAS
Guidance on planning for observation campaigns, i.e. how to design future campaigns so that data collected are also useful for AI training	Expertise to shape measurement strategies and derive higher-level products from raw field data
Field scientists want to understand the capabilities and limitations of current AI prediction systems to better advocate for their data	Several developers offered their operational or experimental models to be used as baselines in community intercomparison exercises
Modellers are seeking standardised protocols: a shared framework to validate their models, not just against skill scores, but against physical realism (stress-testing)	Community input and expertise to help design specific scenarios and diagnostics needed to test physical consistency and process realism
AI developers don't always know what data are available	Observational and model datasets (including campaign data, satellite

	products, and forecast systems) that can be documented and shared
Community and coordination: opportunities to form collaborations and stay informed (mailing list, regular workshops, shared resources)	Active participation in a coordinated network (presenting work, sharing code and data, co-developing benchmarks, and co-authoring syntheses)

3. Presentation Summaries

Introduction to ORCAS

link to slides:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1MwqyqzZpu7YziS-SyLF317RnlGE6HefOkk2SBdLSQmk/edit?usp=sharing>

- ORCAS operates under the World Weather Research Programme's (WWRP) PCAPS project (Polar Coupled Analysis and Prediction for Services), a successor to the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP). It recently became a SCOR (Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research) Working Group.
- The group aims to enhance forecasting capabilities by leveraging new AI techniques, evaluating model performance, and determining optimal observational requirements. A key goal is assessing the physical consistency of AI predictions to build trust among stakeholders.
- Target Outcomes: Safer operations, improved forecasts, targeted observations for future campaigns (e.g., Antarctica InSync, IPY), and user trust.

Modelling: The "Noisy Revolution"

link to slides:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1FMa-GsC2ow8lgF8edtF8gwQ05iHXzzKEZ6KkqocrLcY/edit?usp=sharing>

- AI weather forecasting is undergoing a "noisy revolution," often delivering forecasts that are faster, cheaper, and more accurate than traditional physics-based models.

- New systems like MET-AICE, and ConvLSTM are demonstrating skill in predicting sea ice concentration and extent, often outperforming persistence or climatology baselines.
- Generative AI models (e.g., GenSIM) are showing promise in maintaining physical consistency between variables (e.g., concentration, divergence, and thickness).
- Experiments using the ECMWF AIFS system showed that when sea ice is removed from initial conditions, the model can realistically regenerate sea ice (growing outward from the coasts into the Arctic interior), demonstrating that these models are learning the physics rather than just statistical correlations.

Observations: Field Campaigns in the Age of AI

link to slides:

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1U4l0S7djuA8uYAKhOCE8T_OB21UumSSgW7A6wEsOZnk/edit?usp=sharing

- The slides highlighted how AI was used during the MOSAiC expedition to bridge gaps: optical flow was used to estimate sea ice deformation from noisy, high-frequency ship radar images; machine learning replaced manual classification of SnowMicroPen profiles to reduce operator bias; and deep learning combined Airborne Laser Scanner (ALS) data with SAR backscatter to retrieve sea ice topography.
- Successful AI applications currently favour very large, highly standardised datasets (often from airborne or automated sources) rather than sparse process-study data.
- There remains a challenge in using AI to connect observations across scales (point → airborne → satellite).
- An open question was raised: can AI help discover new process connections from multi-variable campaign data, rather than just encoding known physical relationships?

User Needs and Applications

link to slides:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/19-G0jSZpidrvlmmCQeDXPcCGquHNobAOyTxjY0nyb4M/edit?usp=sharing>

- Users range from maritime operators (shipping/fishing) and Search & Rescue to indigenous communities and climate services.

- Needs differ greatly across time and space scales, and users require information on various variables with thresholds that vary depending on the use case.
- Some of the challenges that emerged from the YOPP include: users are often flooded with undifferentiated data. There is a "more is better" assumption that is often incorrect; users require actionable, tailored information with understandable uncertainty metrics.

4. Community Discussion: Points and Questions Raised

During the facilitated discussions, participants raised the following key points, questions, and concerns. Sub-seasonal to seasonal (S2S) sea ice prediction was identified as the primary initial focus for ORCAS. Shorter timescales (hours to days) and longer timescales (multi-year, decadal) were recognised as important, but the community noted that short-range sea ice prediction remains challenging with current models and observations, while longer timescales are limited by the availability and quality of training datasets. An open question for ORCAS is how far to extend beyond S2S, for example to annual or decadal outlooks and climate services.

Data Standardisation and Benchmarking

Participants saw clear value in WeatherBench-like standardisation for sea ice, particularly for thickness, which would lower the barrier to entry for developers and facilitate model intercomparison. However, the community also recognised that "pure skill" intercomparisons are already underway through initiatives such as SIPN/SIPN South and other efforts. Rather than duplicating these, the suggested niche for ORCAS is to evaluate physical realism and consistency through targeted testing, complementing rather than duplicating existing forecast verification efforts.

The community identified several approaches for this evaluation framework. First, stress-testing and perturbation experiments could probe whether AI models behave physically, e.g., removing sea ice from initial conditions to test whether a model regrows ice realistically from the coasts outward, selecting extreme years (record low or high extents), or artificially masking inputs to test robustness. Second, physical consistency checks could assess whether models maintain plausible relationships across variables, such as whether thickness evolves logically under convergence or divergence, ensuring that AI systems emulate the physics rather than merely learning statistical correlations. Third, case-study-based evaluation could allow a qualitative assessment of the realism of model

output, examining processes such as growth and melt rates, ice-edge evolution, deformation, and Marginal Ice Zone structure, rather than relying solely on global error metrics. Participants also discussed running AI hindcasts over field campaign periods (e.g., the MOSAiC drift) and evaluating not only mean error but the realism of processes and patterns.

For any benchmarking framework, the community discussed both traditional metrics (RMSE, anomaly correlation, ice edge distance) and structural diagnostics (sea ice area, extent, and volume biases; spatial pattern scores), with baselines including persistence, climatology, and selected dynamical models. A shared dataset with clear training, validation, and testing splits was considered essential.

To support these tests, ORCAS could curate existing campaign and process-study datasets (e.g., MOSAiC) into targeted validation suites organised around key physical themes: thermodynamics, dynamics, and snow-ice relationships. The guiding principle for any standardised dataset would be "collection, not perfection": a well-described, unified format to underpin physical consistency tests and verification, not a leaderboard for predictive skill.

Integrating Observations into AI Systems

A major barrier to using field campaign data (e.g., MOSAiC) for training sub-seasonal-to-seasonal (S2S) AI prediction models is the lack of long-term records, typically 20+ years. The community concluded that field observations are best understood not as raw training data for large-scale AI systems, but as sources of derived, standardised products and high-value process benchmarks that can guide, constrain, and improve AI model design and evaluation.

Several approaches were discussed for maximising the value of field data. First, even short or local campaign datasets are extremely valuable for process-level validation and diagnosis (e.g., checking growth and melt rates, evaluating deformation and lead formation, and assessing snow-ice relationships) and could be curated into process-focused validation suites to stress-test AI models and identify systematic physical deficiencies. Second, two-step pipelines can transform sparse field measurements into AI-ready products: for example, during MOSAiC, machine learning was used to derive deformation fields from ship radar, joint snow and ice thickness retrievals from airborne laser scanner transects, and automated snow classification from micro-penetrator profiles. These derived products can then be used for both training (where coverage allows)

and validation. Third, linking campaign data to long records, e.g., by using field measurements to tune satellite retrievals that then produce multi-decadal gridded time series, can bridge the gap between process-rich but temporally limited campaigns and the long records AI systems require. Campaign data can also be used to identify where AI predictions are systematically wrong, informing adjustments to architectures, loss functions, and the choice of input variables and targets.

A key lesson from MOSAiC was that AI and ML applications worked best with large-volume, standardised, automated measurements. For future campaigns, the community suggested it may be more valuable to prioritise fewer sensor types with repeated, high-quality, standardised measurements over diverse but ad hoc instrumentation. More broadly, observers called for early co-design between field scientists and AI modellers, with ORCAS facilitating feedback loops so that campaign design, sampling strategies, and data processing are shaped by what AI systems can actually use.

Direct Observation Prediction (DOP). There was discussion on predicting observations directly (e.g., brightness temperature) rather than gridded variables as an approach that could bypass some known limitations of reanalysis in polar regions. While scientifically attractive, it requires "decoding" to produce products useful to end users (e.g., converting back to ice concentration). DOP was therefore seen as a promising complement to, rather than replacement for, reanalysis-based AI approaches. ORCAS could contribute by identifying which polar observation streams are most suitable for DOP, providing the standardised multi-sensor datasets these models would need, and designing evaluation protocols that check DOP forecasts against independent observations and process metrics.

Can AI handle non-continuous or sparse data? A practical challenge raised was how to enable AI models that require complete gridded fields to ingest sparse, irregular polar observations such as buoys, campaign transects, or satellite swaths. A project focused on African weather was presented as a relevant example. A machine learning model is trained using reanalysis as a "teacher" to learn the mapping from sparse station observations to gridded fields. Once trained, the model can be applied directly to real-world sparse data to produce gridded analyses suitable as input to forecast models, without requiring dense observational coverage. The suggestion for ORCAS was that similar observation-to-grid encoders or graph neural network approaches could map heterogeneous polar observations (buoys, campaign data, satellite swaths) onto gridded sea ice fields. This would offer a more flexible and realistic route to exploiting available polar observations than insisting that everything be turned into a perfectly blended, continuous product first.

Model Diversity

Participants discussed whether the future of AI sea ice prediction lies in a few large, comprehensive models or a diverse ecosystem of tailored systems. The consensus leaned strongly toward diversity, reflecting the heterogeneity of user needs: search and rescue operations require local, high-resolution forecasts on timescales of hours to days, national ice services need regional predictions on timescales of days to weeks, and seasonal outlooks demand basin-scale information over months. Different tasks (e.g., short-range forecasting, sub-seasonal to seasonal prediction, process emulation, and retrieval) may also require fundamentally different model designs.

The group recognised that large, general AI systems (e.g., AIFS-type atmosphere–ocean–sea ice models) are powerful and may serve as backbones providing boundary conditions, but these would likely coexist with more focused systems that are easier to adapt, fine-tune, and interpret for particular applications. A "climate in a bottle" concept was raised as one possible architecture: a coarse-resolution general model that can be tapped and refined through downscaling methods (e.g., diffusion-based generative approaches) to produce higher-resolution or regional forecasts for specific users and timescales.

For ORCAS, the implication is that benchmarks and datasets should be designed to serve this diversity, i.e., usable across different model types, spatial scales, and temporal ranges, and supporting retrieval, emulation, and pure prediction. ORCAS' role is to provide common data and evaluation frameworks within which diverse models can be compared and stress-tested, rather than to prescribe a single architecture for all applications.

User Needs, Scales and Uncertainty

The discussion reinforced that user communities are highly diverse, including maritime operations (shipping, fishing, offshore industries, tourism), national ice services, Search and Rescue, environmental and ecosystem managers, Indigenous communities, research scientists, and climate services and policymakers. Participants noted that these groups operate on very different temporal scales (from hours to seasons and beyond) and spatial scales (local to basin-wide and global), and that even a single group (for example, field teams or ice services) may need information at multiple scales simultaneously.

Building on the presentation, several participants supported the idea that ORCAS could develop a user–requirement matrix that maps, for each user group, the relevant lead times, spatial scales and key variables. There was also agreement that existing experience

from the Polar Prediction Project shows users are often overwhelmed by undifferentiated data and face issues of accessibility, sparsity, and complexity.

In the discussion, this translated into a shared view that ORCAS could help move towards more tailored, actionable information rather than generic products, and that uncertainty needs to be communicated in ways that are meaningful within specific decision contexts. Collaboration with PCAPS task teams is potentially a way forward.

Data Gaps and Operational Barriers

Sea ice thickness was repeatedly flagged as the top-priority data gap. Many products exist from satellite retrievals, models, and field campaigns, but they are fragmented, inconsistent in format, and not easy to use for AI applications. Real-time or near-real-time thickness data are especially limited, constraining operational AI forecasts. The community called for a coherent, standardised thickness collection for both training and validation, following the “collection, not perfection” principle discussed earlier.

A major specific gap is Antarctic sea ice thickness and snow depth. Retrieval algorithms tuned to Arctic conditions do not transfer directly to the Antarctic, where thicker, more complex snow cover with melt–refreeze layering complicates retrievals. Snow is a major source of uncertainty for Antarctic sea ice thickness estimates. The synergy between ICESat-2 and CryoSat-2 offers promise, but questions remain about how much reliable thickness (as opposed to freeboard alone) can be obtained. This makes the Antarctic a critical area of uncertainty compared to the Arctic.

For sub-seasonal to seasonal AI systems, training typically requires 20+ years of continuous hindcasts or observations. Many high-quality observations (e.g., from MOSAiC) are short and episodic and cannot by themselves support S2S AI training. There is a gap in long, consistent, trustworthy polar records, especially for variables beyond sea ice concentration.

Some crucial variables, such as thickness, are not routinely available in near-real time. This creates a disconnect between what can be used for hindcast experiments and research, and what can underpin operational AI forecasts.

Participants highlighted the opportunity to use AI to better connect information across scales and subsystems. In particular, there was interest in linking point and process observations from field campaigns to satellite and basin-scale products, and in exploring joint relationships across the atmosphere–ice–ocean–ecosystem system. The group noted that current products only partially support such cross-scale and cross-system analyses, and saw value in developing systematically prepared “bridge” datasets (e.g.

campaign-derived gridded fields, multi-variable composites) that would make field and process data more usable at the spatial and temporal scales where AI models typically operate.

5. Next Steps

- Establish a mailing list to maintain communication and organise future online check-ins (potentially every 6 months) to keep the community updated on model developments and observational opportunities.
- Circulate this summary document and recordings of the sessions.
- Present the workshop outcomes and open questions at the upcoming PCAPS steering group meeting and explore synergies with other PCAPS Task Teams.
- Target in-person meetings at major conferences to maximise community participation (e.g., Polar AMS, Ocean Sciences, EGU) in 2027.